

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS THROUGH UZBEK FOLK SONGS

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Solving the problem of career-oriented education of music teachers in the field of pedagogy of higher educational institutions of our republic includes not only improving certain aspects of the educational and pedagogical process, but also a fundamental revision of its conceptual foundations. . A bachelor's degree provides in-depth knowledge, skills and abilities in one of the areas of higher education [1] the essence of this educational process is, first of all, to determine the professional training of the teacher of this specialty and the content, forms and methods of improving his professional training in the general system of education. Taking into account some conclusions of scientists and specialists (V.V. Kraevskii, M.Skatkin, etc.), it should be mentioned that the solution to this problem can only be achieved through a clear didactic approach to the professional training of future music teachers. It can be done in the process of special scientific understanding and justification as an entity. The logical basis of such reasoning in accordance with pedagogical theory and requirements is the movement from the theoretical representation of the object (professional training) to the construction of a clear system of its content, forms and tools [2]. It is possible to recognize the general theoretical idea of improving professional training by means of Uzbek folk songs as the essence of the scientific-pedagogical justification carried out in this study. At the theoretical level, the result of such justification is the strict structures of special scientific analysis, such as "content", "tasks", "form" and "methods". The final goal of the specified research task is to determine the content, theoretical foundations, methodological ways and tools of future music teachers through the medium of Uzbek folk singing, the content of this training together with its legal component [3].

In the philosophical and general professional pedagogical methodology, it is emphasized that any specific scientific research should be based on methodological foundations and guidelines. This, in turn, determines the logic and methods of research, allows to predict its results (theory, content, logical and reasonable components, etc.) [4]. Based on this, the following approaches

are proposed, which envisage the author's socio-pedagogical and didactic holistic analysis of the object as the initial position determining the author's position in solving the research task:

- a) social status requirements in connection with the social life and practice of the population;
- b) in the context of the comprehensive system of professional training of future music teachers;
- c) taking into account the specific conditions and characteristics of the content and activity of professional training through the medium of Uzbek folk songs in the higher musical and pedagogical education system.

The content of professional training of future music teachers is primarily determined by the needs of social order, pedagogical theory and practice, and actually acts as their own form of expression. Pedagogy related to improving the basics of professional training of the future music teacher, creating optimal conditions for their creative development as a specialist in the future, improving the level of professionally oriented methodological thinking reflects the most important trend of professional music education [10].

In determining the essence of the main tasks in the professional training of future music teachers, first of all, the appearance, content, form and style of the object in the system of relationships, relying on its general philosophical meaning, at the same time from a socio-pedagogical point of view in terms of the overall process of improving the professional training of a music teacher, the most important factor affects the overall development of a music teacher's personality - his motivational, value, intellectual and activity areas [10].

In the process of professional training of future music teachers, the specialist's thinking and working style are rapidly rebuilt, creative professional potential is enriched. In the system of music education in the field of pedagogy, professional training mainly functions as a cognitive direction. Because it helps undergraduate students to actively gather knowledge in various genres of science and singing. It serves to understand their socio-professional and personal value. On the basis of this knowledge, future specialists will acquire the necessary ways of knowing and changing the musical-pedagogical reality. They will have the experience of using them creatively in their practice. The integrated approach implemented in the process of professional training helps to establish interdisciplinary relations, and this, in turn, creates completely new conditions for systematizing and expanding the thinking experience of future music teachers.

Musical-pedagogical education not only ensures the implementation of professional knowledge available in the experience of future specialists in various fields of science and music art (aesthetics, pedagogy, musicology, performer, theory, practice, etc.). Also, a consistent understanding of the essence of this knowledge, the decisive role in the implementation of a didactic, systematically integrated approach to the study of relevant professional problems is considered important. It is about multi-faceted, pedagogical connection of musical education process with different levels of professionally oriented professional knowledge (pedagogical, professional, scientific, private) in general social-pedagogical practice (school-education-training) and other aspects. Lajak directs to the synthesis of the ideas of music teachers and professional training. In it, certain empirical facts and events in music lessons are understood not only from a professional, but also from a methodological point of view, that is, the general laws of the musical pedagogical process are understood through the scientific and theoretical foundations of the prism art. Pedagogical conditions for improvement and implementation of professional training have been defined and the following have been defined:

- students have the ability to sing and play musical instruments, have musical-theoretical knowledge, and have developed abilities, skills, and performance skills;
- sufficient teaching-methodical, material and technical support, conditions for the use of advanced digital technologies in teaching;
- control and self-monitoring of students and young people's mastery of educational programs and independent education, individual, ensemble, and team improvement of performance skills [6].

The descriptive function of professional training lies in its unique stimulating effect of personal, artistic and cognitive, valuable thinking and activity of future music teachers [5]. In the process of forming a methodological professional musical culture, each of them is given the right to choose a method of acquiring methodological knowledge and methods of activity that best meets the general and professional individual-personal desires and opportunities. The content and process of professional training based on a personal approach, first of all, to awaken the creative self-awareness of the future music teacher, to develop his spiritual world, to develop the ability to self-awareness aimed at creating favorable conditions in the audience.

It is natural that the process of improving professional training will bring significant changes. The nature of the holistic process of teaching and upbringing

is related to raising this process to a metaphysical, reproductive and dialectical, creative level. This makes it possible to talk about another important content of training for professional training – heuristics [7]. The process of developing the creative and professional thinking of undergraduate students is primarily determined by the nature of the methods of activity characterized by methodological knowledge, generality and pedagogical mobility. According to H. Santulo, an experienced scientist, it shows that "strong heuristic ability is associated with the promotion of effective ideas, the development of a strategy for scientific research, and the stimulation of theoretical synthesis." The mechanism and logic of the disclosure and assimilation of this knowledge is compared to search and research activities, which provides the means of describing the problems in its content and the search for ways to solve them - analysis of search results.

The reflexive-heuristic nature of the professional training of the music teacher was manifested, first of all, through its dialogic quality. Here, the future music teacher carries out several practices and "communicates" at the same time. In particular, to analyze the activities of the dialogue-music teacher, to reflect the objective and subjective importance of the problems of music pedagogy and the knowledge necessary for their study; internal dialogue - demonstrating the unique performance skills of communication with music and participants of the music-pedagogical process (professors, concertmasters, musicians, students).

The presence of dialogue in the process of professional training helps to form a creative, methodologically oriented way of thinking in the future music teacher, the main features of which are "pre-reflection", empathic and creative attitude.

The heuristic effect of professional training on the overall process of musical-pedagogical education, the professional knowledge and methods of activity acquired by specialists in the future are important for creativity in other disciplines, including special training. In this regard, methodological analysis has a special place, future music teachers are required to carry out any search and creative work (writing reports and messages within the framework of research and development, understanding artistic and performing, musical and theoretical problems, in the practice of higher pedagogical education in various when conducting various experimental works, etc.) they should feel. The provision of professional knowledge and activity methods leading to various areas of professional training, on the one hand, confirms the didactic nature of these knowledge and methods, and on the other hand, indicates that they have a place in the development of creative abilities of future specialists.

The obvious manifestation of heuristic education for improving the professional training of a future music teacher is the fundamentalization of its content, that is, the conceptualization of the future music teacher's thinking [8]. On the basis of professional scientific research (V.N. Rostorguev, B.C. Shubinskiy, etc.), such relationships, knowledge, which provide not only a nomination, but also a scientifically based basis of theoretical or professional hypotheses, ideas and concepts in a specific professional field at the personal level. and skills development. Its content and process is music education of pedagogy aimed at developing such thinking and restoring the social reputation of the "authorship" approach.

The process of professional training includes not only the task of arming the future music teacher with professional knowledge and creative experience of their application, but also the formation of a certain valuable attitude to the process of knowing and changing the musical-pedagogical reality [9]. The effect of this training on moral-value aspects of the mind and activity of the future teacher is evidence of the fulfillment of his axiological task. Their essence is that the content of professional training is not only a source of professional reflection on various phenomena and processes of musical and pedagogical reality for students, but also serves as a basis for forming a personal and valuable attitude to this aspect of their professional and creative activity.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonuni // Xalq so'zi. – Toshkent, 2020. – 24 sentyabr. – B. 1-2.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi pedagogik ta'lim kontseptsiyasi. – Toshkent: O'zR XTV, O'zPFITI, 1995. – 20 b.
3. Muslimov N.A. Bo'lajak kasb ta'limi o'qituvchilarini kasbiy shakllantirish. Toshkent, Fan, 2004
4. Abdullaeva Q.M. Maxsus fanlarni o'qitishda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy bilim va ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning metodik asoslari: Dis. ... ped. fan.nom. – Toshkent, 2006. – B. 182.
5. Muslimov N.A. Bo'lajak o'qituvchining loyihalash faoliyati. 2012. O'quv qo'llanma. 6,1 b.t.
6. Panjiev Q.B. O'zbek xalq qo'shiqchilik ijodiyoti. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent, 2021. – B. 274.
7. Tolipova J. O'qituvchilarning kompetentligiga qo'yiladigan talablar. Metodik qo'llanma. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2010. – B. 125
8. Xolikov A.A. Pedagogik mahorat. Monografiya. Toshkent: Iqtisod-moliya, 2011. – B. 418.

9. Hoshimov K., Nishonova S. Pedagogika tarixi: Darslik. – Toshkent: Alisher Navoiy nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy kutubxonasi, 2005. – B. 304.
10. Panjiev Q.B. O‘zbek xalq qo‘shiqchiligi vositasida bo‘lajak musiqa o‘qituvchilarini kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish. Monografiya. T.: Maxalla va oila nashriyoti. 2021. – 200

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